

THE COORDINATION OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL TRAINING IN ACHIEVING HIGH RESULTS OF AN ATHLETE

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ABSTRACT

In the following proverb, the correct organization of athletics training is the guarantee of obtaining high results. Information is given on the methods of application of the coach.

Student activity in the educational process has been and remains one of the main principles of didactics. Pupil activity is the result of goal-directed managerial pedagogical influences and the organization of the pedagogical environment. Pedagogical business game is one of the teaching technologies that ensures students' activity. Interest in game activity is provided by the elements of competition, which satisfy the needs of students such as self-expression and realization.

A great feature of the game is that it is both development and learning at the same time.

Pedagogical game is determined by the clearly set goal of teaching and the corresponding pedagogical result. These results are based on educational preparation activities.

Pedagogical games are described according to the game style as follows: by subjects; plot; business, imitation, dramatized games.

In the educational process, businessmen use various forms of games: imitation, operational, role-playing games, working theater, psycho and sociodramas.

Imitation games - the activity of a department, workshop, enterprise organization is simulated. The script of simulation games, in addition to the plot of the event, includes details about the composition and importance of the process and objects to be simulated.

Operational games - they model the relevant work process, the conditions for their execution. They help to master certain specific operations: - solving problems, a certain method.

Role-playing games - the mental states and behavior of a certain person in the performance of duties and responsibilities are worked out, roles are assigned with mandatory content.

Business theater is a situation and the behavior of a person in this situation is developed. A scenario is drawn up with the details of the situation, the tasks and obligations of the participants, and the goals. Here, it is important to get into the true image of a certain person, understand his behavior, assess the situation and choose the right course of action.

Psychodrama and sociodrama are similar to a role-playing game, business theater, only here socio-psychological issues are solved. Such issues include the ability to feel the situation in the team, the ability to correctly assess the mental state of another person and change it, and the ability to communicate effectively with him.

Game preparation stage. This stage, in turn, consists of two parts: development of the game, introduction to the game. Game development - includes development of the game script, creation of instructions and provision of material support.

Literal mental development is impossible without play. The game is a spark that arouses enthusiasm and interest in learning in students.

The game is a method used by adults - teachers, educators, parents - to form certain qualities in elementary school students. With the help of the game, the learning process of students becomes easier, they learn to deal with various objects, and also the culture of behavior is formed in them.

The child's personality is formed by means of the game, in which the mental characteristics related to the organization of educational and work activities and entering into relations with people are formed in the future.

Through play, children learn about existence and try to change the world. Thus, the game lays the foundation for the formation of human activity. In the game, a person shows the ability to reflect existence. The most important importance of the game is that the child's need to influence the world first appears and is formed in it.

A didactic game is an active activity in the field of creating an imitation model of the studied events and phenomena. An important difference of the game from other types of activity is that its subject is human activity. The main type of activity in the didactic game is cooperative learning activity.

In a didactic game, it is important to have educational tasks that take into account the mastery of students. When creating this or that form of didactic games, the leading adults should pay attention to the types that are interesting for children and attract their attention.

An important feature of didactic games that differs from other types of activities is the strictness of its content. The structural components of didactic games are as follows: game logic, game action, game rules.

The logic of the game is mainly reflected in its title. In the course of the game, an opportunity is created to increase the cognitive activity of students, to show their abilities, to use their knowledge, skills and abilities to achieve the goal of the game.

The rules of the game help to organize the game process correctly. He regulates the students' behavior and their interactions. In didactic games, a certain result is achieved, the final of which indicates its completion. A certain didactic goal is set in the game, and the achievement of this goal creates a sense of spiritual and mental satisfaction in students. Didactic games are always an indicator of students' learning or practical application of learned knowledge for the teacher. In children's education, didactic games are used in two

directions: to form a perfect person and for narrow didactic purposes. The game is the main form of student activity. The game is one of the important types of mental activity, in which all types of the student's abilities develop, his imagination about the world expands, and the richness of his speech increases. Didactic games have an effective effect on the development of various abilities, perception, speech and attention of the student.

Currently, pedagogues are creating games with ready content and rules. Specific rules are given in the games that serve to form certain qualities in the personality of the child. Games with ready-made rules and content are characterized by the following features: the idea and task of the game are carried out under the influence of the game. The idea (or task) of the game and the effect of the game constitute the content of the game; the influence of the game and the relations of the players are governed by the rules of the game. Rules and ready-made game content help students organize the game independently.

Arousing students' interest in knowledge through didactic games is effective if it is organized based on their interests. In such cases, the child always has a desire to know the news, an interest in knowledge arises. Regular development and strengthening of interest in knowledge will raise the attitude of the students of the small school to study and increase the level of mastery. Interest in knowledge teaches a junior high school student to search, and he learns to search for answers to various questions. The student's inquisitive activity develops in him the feeling of emotional upliftment and joy of success. Interest in learning not only positively affects the outcome of the process, but also affects the active development of mental processes such as thinking, perception, memory, and attention.

Interest in learning is one of the motivations that increase students' interest in studying. Its influence will be very strong. Stimulating curiosity can help even slow learners to work effectively.

In a properly organized pedagogical process, if the activities of students and educational activities are systematically and regularly organized, interest in learning becomes one of the main qualities of the learner's personality and has a strong influence on his development.

In conclusion, it can be said that interest in knowledge becomes a powerful tool of the educational process. Abu Rayhan Beruni emphasized that it is an important task to interest students in the educational process, and in his book "Memorials from ancient peoples", "The goal is not to prolong the sentence, but not to bore the student, because always looking at the same thing leads to boredom and impatience. As the student moves from subject to subject, he seems to be walking in different gardens. Before you can see one, the other begins, and that person is interested in seeing them and wants to look at them, as it is said that everything has its own taste. "The same thing is tiring, makes the memory dull."

It is impossible to make the student interested in knowledge without activating his cognitive activity. That is why in the educational process, the student's constant interest in knowledge is the most important means of educational education, development of his motivation to study. In this way, the interest in learning helps the realization of all the possibilities in the personality of the student.

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